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Environmental Regulation

Understanding and modelling hydrological non-stationarity in South-West Western Australia

Research project | Final report

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Photo: Donnelly River at One Tree Bridge. Credit: Creative Commons

Executive Summary

Hydrological non-stationarity has been a lived reality in many south-west rivers over the last fifty years, and it presents a key risk for future water planning. Hydrological non-stationarity means that a year of given rainfall provides less streamflow today than it did in years past, due to a shift in the relationship between rainfall and runoff. Two challenges that arise are to:

1. Improve understanding of hydrological processes that drive this non-stationarity so that we can explain historical observations and spatial patterns, and to give insight into whether further shifts are likely in future; and
2. Ensure models adequately represent those hydrological processes, such that they match historical observations and can be considered trustworthy for future planning purposes.

To examine this in more detail, the Department of Water and Environmental Regulation (DWER) has commissioned a study by the University of Melbourne.

This report. As the final report for the above project, this document presents steps towards both goals. For the first, we describe an effort to systematically catalogue which catchments experienced shifts and when these shifts occurred, using cutting edge techniques. In addition, we include a literature review of current knowledge both in academic journals and in reports commissioned locally by the various branches of the Government of Western Australia. Towards the second goal, we present the results of a wide range of modelling tests applied to nine different rainfall-runoff models, aimed at characterising the strengths and weaknesses of currently available modelling approaches, and at identifying next steps to improve outcomes. All analyses are based on a broad set of 76 catchments from across the south-west.

Outcomes towards improved understanding. The results of two distinct analyses confirm that hydrological non-stationarity is widespread across the region, with Hidden Markov Modelling (after Peterson et al. 2021) indicating non-stationarity in 49 out of 75 catchments. Consistent with expectations, the most common transition point occurred around the year 2000, with 30 out of 49 catchments transitioning to a lower streamflow regime at about this time. Perhaps surprisingly, few catchments show a hydrological transition in the 1970s despite changes in rainfall occurring around this time. The size of the shift (i.e. the volume of streamflow that is "missing") was correlated with land use, specifically with the proportion of the catchment that is forested. This is consistent with the literature review which found that such areas have been the subject of significant groundwater declines, in contrast to non-forested areas whose historical clearing has often led to decadal (and in some cases ongoing) increases in groundwater levels. The literature review emphasises the importance of the unique hydrogeology of many areas within the south-west, and its interaction with land use changes. Overall, the long hydrological "memory" of groundwater systems is an important driver of interannual and decadal river flow dynamics.

Outcomes towards improved modelling. The south-west rivers provide a unique test of ability for rainfall-runoff models and the results clearly identify some leading models, although more work is required. The main findings were:

- a) **Model choice:** The results highlighted the LASCAM model as one which can represent the observed historical multi-annual dynamics, along with (to a lesser extent) SACRAMENTO and a variant of GR4J specifically designed to harbour long-term groundwater trends. In contrast, certain simple models (e.g. original GR4J, SIMHYD) performed poorly and results suggest these models should be avoided.
- b) **Objective functions:** the tests also revealed practical insights into choice of objective function; results suggest avoiding traditional options (e.g. Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency, or NSE) in favour of objective functions

Executive Summary

such as the “Split Trotter” that separately consider high and low flow conditions; and dry and wet years (and possibly weighting the drier years more).

- c) **Ability under changing climate:** Despite these promising and useful insights, results indicate that existing models (including LASCAM) lack the ability to extrapolate to climatic conditions that are different from those under which they were calibrated. This result, which is not unique to Western Australia, is worrying because climate change impact assessments require models which can operate reliably despite future changes in climate beyond historical norms. The result suggests the need for better understanding of key processes and translation into improved models.
- d) **Future climate change test results:** Given the tendency of models to underestimate the severity of streamflow reductions, we would expect that improved methods or models may exhibit a greater sensitivity to change when used to provide streamflow projections under climate change. We ran a "future climate change" streamflow simulation which confirmed that this is indeed the case for the methods recommended under (a) and (b). Thus, despite the problems in (c), this report recommends to adopt the LASCAM model calibrated with an objective function called the "Weighted Split Trotter" for the purposes of planning, as an interim measure while further research is conducted.

Next steps. To make LASCAM more useable in practice, it is recommended that the model structure is reviewed to understand which parameters contribute the least to the overall flow prediction. Armed with this understanding, it may be possible to produce a simpler version of LASCAM that is both more understandable and quicker/easier to reliably calibrate. Model review may also incorporate a specific analysis of groundwater dynamics with reference to available bore and/or satellite data, to make simulations more robust in catchments experiencing non-stationarity due to groundwater decline. A systematic review of groundwater data may also provide further context to explain the spatial patterns of hydrological non-stationarity revealed by the Hidden Markov modelling.

In addition to this, research is recommended into revised calibration techniques, including (i) continued effort on objective functions that focus on the most relevant parts of the historical streamflow record; and (ii) methods that use non-streamflow types of information such as actual evapotranspiration and groundwater data. The poor extrapolation results for otherwise robust models (such as LASCAM) may be remedied by giving the model more varied information during calibration, and identifying and emphasising the most relevant aspects of this information.

The methods undertaken here focussed on a large sample of catchments, in order to maximise generalisability. It is recommended that future research complement this large sample approach with detailed studies of selected cases that are deemed to be important to water resource planning and/or representative of broader planning areas.

Conclusions. This project has provided an initial assessment of the regional relevance of current modelling and procedures to water planning. It is pleasing to see that the results affirm the use of a model that is already actively used by DWER, namely the LASCAM model. At the same time, it has revealed limitations in the transferability of models, with implications for robustness of modelling under climate change. More robust modelling solutions will require ongoing research, and in the meantime this report has provided evidence-based interim recommendations for modelling to support water resource planning.

Data and code. All input data, code required for analysis and output results is freely available at the following public repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13374404>

1	Introduction.....	1
2	Improved understanding of hydrological non-stationarity.....	2
2.1	Introduction.....	2
2.2	Methods.....	2
2.2.1	Data Selection.....	2
2.2.2	Identifying shifts in rainfall-runoff relationship.....	3
2.2.3	Method 1: Linear Regression after Saft et al. (2015).....	4
2.2.4	Method 2: Hidden Markov Modelling after Peterson et al. (2021).....	4
2.2.5	Notes on data processing.....	5
2.2.6	Land cover.....	5
2.3	Results.....	5
2.3.1	Method 1 results (Linear Regression).....	5
2.3.2	Method 2 results (Hidden Markov Modelling using HydroState).....	5
2.3.3	Relationship between hydrological non-stationarity and land cover.....	9
2.4	Literature review of dominant processes and drivers.....	11
2.4.1	Review by region.....	11
2.4.2	Process interactions among climate, land use and groundwater.....	13
2.4.3	Synthesis and discussion.....	14
3	Improved modelling of hydrological non-stationarity.....	16
3.1	Questions explored via modelling tests.....	16
3.2	Methods for each test.....	17
3.2.1	Coverage test.....	17
3.2.2	Differential split sample test.....	18
3.2.3	Climate change test.....	18
3.3	Methodological and data considerations applicable to all tests.....	18
3.3.1	Data.....	18
3.3.2	Model selection.....	18
3.3.3	Objective function selection.....	18
3.4	Results.....	20
3.4.1	Coverage Testing.....	20
3.4.2	Differential split sample testing.....	21
3.4.3	Climate change test.....	23
3.4.4	Inspection of timeseries.....	25

3.5	Discussion	26
3.6	Limitations	27
3.7	Recommendations for modelling	29
4	Next steps	30
5	Conclusion	30
6	References	31
7	Appendices	36

1 Introduction

Changes to the global climate have seen a consistent decline in rainfall across the rivers in South-West Western Australia (SWWA) since the mid-1970s (Hope et al., 2006). This reduction puts pressure on water resources in this region, reducing dam inflows (Smith and Power, 2014) and recharge to groundwater storage (Gelsinari et al., 2024; Priestly et al., 2023) which support urban and rural populations. The decline in streamflow triggered by the reduced precipitation has been highly non-linear in some locations, with a streamflow reduction of up to 70% seen in some catchments, where rainfall has only reduced 15-20% (Hughes et al., 2012; Kinal and Stoneman, 2012). To understand water availability and plan for the future within this region, better understanding is required of these rainfall-runoff interactions and the processes that drive them. To this end, the Department of Water and Environmental Regulation (DWER) have commissioned the University of Melbourne to better understand hydrological non-stationarity in the south west rivers and to identify the most robust available models (and modelling methods). The overall objective is to improve the quality of information available to inform decisions in the water sector.

Some academic research has investigated the rainfall-runoff changes, such as Hughes et al. (2012), Kinal and Stoneman (2012), and Petrone et al. (2010). However, research has not been rolled out systematically over wide areas—for example, by conducting a consistent analysis across a large sample of catchments in south west rivers, to identify spatial and temporal patterns. Thus, a key question is: *Where and when did shifts in rainfall-runoff relationship occur?* This is the focus of Section 2 of this report, which also contains a review and synthesis of literature (both academic and government reports) examining the physical processes responsible for changes in streamflow generation.

Current rainfall-runoff models tend to underestimate the sensitivity to long-term changes in average rainfall, meaning that they cannot match historic streamflow declines and are unreliable for future planning. If we do not effectively capture non-stationarity in our assessment of water availability, we are likely to overestimate runoff and water available for use under a future climate that is likely to be hotter and drier than historical climate conditions. Certain models such as GR4J and LASCAM have seen wider use in the region, but it is possible that other models may be better suited, of which there are many candidates. Existing studies such as Fowler et al. (2016) and Hughes et al. (2021) only tested models on a handful of catchments and for a small number of models. Thus, key questions include: *Which current rainfall-runoff model(s) work best in south west rivers? How well do they work when calibrated using state-of-the-art techniques?* These questions are the focus of Section 3. Section 4 provides recommended next steps with a focus on improving modelling outcomes, while Section 5 concludes the report.

Overall, this body of work is envisaged as an initial step towards more robust modelling outcomes. The project has aimed to align existing research—much of which was conducted elsewhere, particularly in response to the Millennium Drought in south east Australia—to the south west rivers context. By road testing these methods on catchments locally, it can be determined which method and knowledge are, or are not, transferable given the unique environment and context of the south west. Having synthesised these learnings with existing local knowledge and the empirical tests described herein, we can then assess remaining knowledge gaps and formulate a plan towards more robust modelling in the south west rivers.

2 Improved understanding of hydrological non-stationarity

2.1 Introduction

The essence of hydrological non-stationarity is a disproportionate reduction to streamflow in relation to rainfall reduction, behaviour reported first in Australia but since seen in several locations globally (e.g. Hughes et al., 2012; Saft et al., 2015; Fowler et al., 2021). To develop an understanding of this phenomenon, the following two challenges arise:

- (i) **Application of consistent definitions/procedures across space:** The first challenge is to decide what “disproportionate” means in terms of streamflow reductions, and define mathematical procedures for characterising this. These procedures then need to be consistently rolled out across space and over the entire historic record of streamflow, to identify when and where such reductions have occurred. In addition to being relevant for water planning, the resulting spatial and temporal patterns are instructive for forming hypotheses as to the causes of non-stationarity.
- (ii) **Understanding hydrological processes:** although streamflow is above-ground and thus easier to measure, many core processes driving non-stationarity are not easily measurable due to occurring in the subsurface or being related to distributed factors such as land cover. Thus, having described spatial and temporal patterns using the tests above, the search for an explanation should also synthesise knowledge from related areas such as groundwater hydrology and from records of, e.g. historical land use.

This section is intended to respond to these challenges. Sections 2.2-2.3 answer (i) by applying existing techniques that provide clear definitions and statistical tests to indicate non-stationarity. Section 2.4 provides an initial response to (ii) by reviewing available literature on the south-west, both in academic journals and government reports.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Data Selection

The set of catchments that is used both in this section and for rainfall-runoff modelling in Section 3 is described in this section. Both components use data from 76 catchments within the south west of Western Australia (Figure 1). The catchments cover from Hill River to Stirling Range National Park, with two additional catchments further east towards Esperance. These selected areas span the Perth Basin including the Swan and Scott Coastal Plains, and the Dandaragan and Blackwood Plateaux; the Darling Plateau and Ranges; and the Albany-Fraser Orogen, enveloping a variation of topography, geology and climate. Study area selection was conducted in collaboration with DWER, ensuring that the analysis covered catchments of concern and those which required consideration for future planning.

Daily streamflow data for the majority of catchments were obtained from the CAMELS-AUS database which is itself based on the Hydrological Reference Stations of the Bureau of Meteorology. The CAMELS-AUS database also provides information regarding catchment land use. For stations not in CAMELS-AUS that were deemed by DWER to be desirable, streamflow data was obtained directly from DWER. Daily precipitation data for each catchment were obtained from the SILO database (<http://www.longpaddock.qld.gov.au/silo>). Section 3’s rainfall-runoff modelling analysis also required potential evapotranspiration data, for which SILO’s *Morton Wet Environment Evaporation* was used, consistent with several Australian rainfall-runoff modelling studies.

Figure 1 – Map of catchments adopted across SWWA. CAMELS-AUS catchments in blue with additional catchments provided by DWER in pink (DWER, 2024).

Catchment selection aimed to avoid catchments with significant extractions in order to understand processes linked to non-stationarity, rather than direct human impacts. This was unavoidable in some cases, however, with farm dams existing in some catchments which were seen to be of significance to DWER and the analysis as a whole. This is further discussed in the limitations (Section 3.6).

2.2.2 Identifying shifts in rainfall-runoff relationship

Two methods to identify a shift in the rainfall-runoff relationship were applied to the selected study sites. The first was a method similar to Saft et al. (2015) and is useful here as it provides a clear visual representation of non-stationarity. The second was the method of Peterson et al. (2021; namely the open-source R Package, HydroState).

This latter method was used to objectively determine if and when shifts occurred. Both methods are explained below.

2.2.3 Method 1: Linear Regression after Saft et al. (2015)

Saft et al. (2015) examined a large sample of headwater catchments across south-east Australia and developed a new test to determine whether shifts in rainfall-runoff relationship had occurred in each case. The method was relatively simple, consisting of (i) aggregating the data to annual timestep; (ii) applying a transformation to the streamflow data so that the relationship with rainfall becomes linear; (iii) drawing a line of best fit to the streamflow data before the apparent shift, and separately after the apparent shift (forcing each to have an equal gradient); and (iv) undertaking a statistical test to determine whether the difference in vertical position (i.e. y intercept) of the lines of best fit was statistically significant.

A limitation of this method is that the adopted periods require pre-definition rather than arising naturally from the analysis. On the other hand, the plots arising from this method are intuitively easy to grasp and are thus an excellent communication tool. Thus, here we primarily use this method to provide a clear visual representation of non-stationarity. We do apply lines of best fit, using periods based on consultation with DWER and consistent with literature about the timing of climatic changes (e.g. Hope et al. 2006). Specifically, three periods are adopted, namely before 1975, 1975-1999 and 2000-2021.

Prior to splitting, the aforementioned transformation was applied, specifically a Box-Cox (Box & Cox, 1964) transformation with the Box-Cox parameter chosen such that skew was minimised and the distribution became approximately normal. For any period with greater than 10 data points (10 years of data), a linear model was fit which used a previously determined slope but varied the intercept. The slope was predetermined using a regression analysis of the Box-Cox transformed data over all three periods. All models were fit through minimising the sum squared difference between the modelled and actual streamflow.

2.2.4 Method 2: Hidden Markov Modelling after Peterson et al. (2021)

Working with over 150 catchments in Victoria, Peterson et al. (2021) developed an alternative method to characterise rainfall-runoff shifts. The particular focus for this study was the question of post-drought recovery: it demonstrated that the catchments had not recovered (hydrologically speaking—that is, they shifted but did not shift back) even seven years after the end of the Millennium Drought. Because of this focus, it would be inappropriate to pre-define when a given catchment shifted or recovered; this had to arise naturally out of the method used (in contrast to the above). Peterson et al. (2021) developed a special type of Hidden Markov modelling to characterise this. Hidden Markov modelling assumes there is a “hidden state” which explain and modulates the relationship between inputs (in this case, rainfall) and outputs (in this case, streamflow), and that this state cannot be directly observed but only inferred from the input and output data.

The aggregated and infilled data was input into the open-source R-Package, HydroState (Peterson et al., 2021). This fitted several different Hidden Markov models to the data, with 1, 2 or 3 hidden states allowed. While individual models were fitted by performance, the choice of the “best” model for each catchment was based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) which penalises models with more free parameters. Thus, for catchments that are reported to never change state, the meaning of this is that the additional performance of the more complex 2- or 3-state models was not sufficient to justify the additional parameters. Of the many options allowed by HydroState, we adopted the Box-Cox transform instead of log and the Gamma distribution rather than the truncated Gaussian (both for reasons of flexibility).

The outputs from HydroState included predicted total streamflow for a given year based on the model with the lowest AIC, in addition to a prediction of what the total streamflow would be if the catchment remained in the normal flow state for that year, with these values reported for the extent of the gauging period. To inform the post analysis, a metric was calculated for every catchment, quantifying how different the predicted and normal flow states were. This was quantified as an average annual value, in millimetres equivalent depth, where the reported value refers to the amount of water that is “missing” when the adopted HydroState annual flow timeseries is compared with the HydroState annual flow timeseries if the catchment had not exhibited non-stationarity (i.e. had

remained in a “normal” flow state for the entire time period). This difference was mapped to understand its spatial variation.

2.2.5 Notes on data processing

Gaps in streamflow data were present for most of the catchments, which present a problem when aggregating to annual timestep (as required by both the above methods). Where missing days constituted less than 5% of days in a given year, these days were infilled by fitting a linear relationship between the streamflow in the catchment of interest and the nearest catchment with data on that given day. The analysis using HydroState required continuous data, as such, years were infilled using the same method where it reasonably facilitated the analysis of a greater stretch of time.

Streamflow and precipitation data were aggregated according to water years from May to April of the following year. This was intended to include the majority of flows triggered by the start of the seasonally high rainfall, while coinciding with periods of lowered irrigation demand.

2.2.6 Land cover

Two extra analyses were undertaken to explore the relationship between the reported non-stationarity and spatial patterns of land cover. Both analyses had a particular focus on the land cover types associated with trees, since the influence of forest on the hydrological cycle was a key outcome of the literature review (see Section 2.4). The first of the analyses plotted the land cover proportions (expressed as percentages) for each catchment, and the plot groups together all catchments exhibiting non-stationarity, while those that did not were grouped separately. The land cover proportions were shown in three separate groups: “closed” forest (which is a single category in the adopted dataset), other land covers associated with trees; and all other land covers.

The second analysis regressed two variables: firstly, the proportion of each catchment taken up by closed forest, since this was the single land use most strongly correlated with non-stationarity outcomes; and secondly, the metric defining the average annual missing streamflow, as described above.

The catchments in this analysis were limited to those from the CAMELS-AUS dataset (54 catchments) due to the readily available land cover data, meaning the additional catchments selected in collaboration with DWER were not included. The land cover information is from the Dynamic Land Cover Dataset (DLDC; <https://researchdata.edu.au/dynamic-land-cover-version-21/1278349>).

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Method 1 results (Linear Regression)

The linear regression results after Saft et al. (2015) vividly demonstrate that hydrological non-stationarity is present in many catchments of the south west, as expected. The full set for all 76 catchments is provided in Appendix A.1.1, while Figure 2 shows results for nine selected catchments. Figure 2 shows how streamflow in later years (particularly post-2000) exhibit “drift” downwards indicating less streamflow for a given rainfall amount. However, the story was not consistent across the whole sample. Four interesting variants on the results are highlighted in Figure 3, one of which (Goodga River at Black Cat) shows that it was possible for catchments to start in a lower streamflow state prior to 1975 and then increase to a higher streamflow state post-1975, only to reduce again post-2000. Others experienced no change in rainfall-runoff relationship, such as the Tone River at Bulilup. As mentioned above, some catchments lacked adequate data to fit a relationship within certain periods, which is why the pre-1975 line is missing from many panels in Figure 2. Note that mapped results are held over until Section 2.3.2.

2.3.2 Method 2 results (Hidden Markov Modelling using HydroState)

The results from HydroState are consistent with the linear regression in some locations but offer further insight into the changes in the rainfall-runoff relationship, particularly with respect to timing of shifts. Figure 4 shows a sample of the full HydroState output for two catchments. The precipitation and observed flow across time are shown, with scattered points on the flow timeseries indicating the flow state predicted through modelling. If the flow state in a

given year is not changed relative to the flow state in the first year of flow record (called “normal” here), it changes colour. In this case it means the flow is significantly different to what would be expected if the earlier rainfall-runoff relationship had persisted. The predicted streamflow had that earlier relationship persisted is also shown (hollow circles), and thus the difference between the hollow and filled circles is the “missing water” arising from the non-stationarity. Contrasting to the linear regression, Ordnanace Road Crossing only has one distinct change in flow regime, while National Park shows two.

Figure 5 collates the number of catchments in a given state for a given year, with the proportion of catchments in that state plotted. A large portion of catchments indicated a change in flow state just after 2000. Interestingly, few catchments show a hydrological shift in the 1970s, despite the changes in climatic conditions that occurred at this time. Note the small numbers on the x axis showing the sample size. The sample size is smaller in earlier years because fewer gauges were active. The majority of catchments have data from around 1990 onwards, while a handful of catchments cease monitoring from 2000.

Figure 6 shows the spatial distribution of shifted catchments for the years 1975, 2001 and 2020. The catchments exhibiting shifts are relatively well spread across the landscape, with some in the Blackwood and Darling Plateaux, some towards the north of the Perth Basin and some nearing Albany. There are few broad patterns, although arguably the drier catchments further from the coast appear less likely to exhibit non-stationarity. In addition, the catchments east of Denmark on the south coast, from Albany through to Esperance, showed no non-stationarity. Likewise, cleared wheatbelt catchments such as those in the Murray River (614224, 614006 and 614196) also showed no non-stationarity, and this will be discussed further below. Figure 7 shows that the extent of “missing” water follows a similar pattern, with the greatest missing volumes within the Perth Basin and Blackwood Plateau.

Figure 2 – Annual precipitation and Box-Cox transformed streamflow for selected catchments, with fitted relationships.

Figure 3 – Same as Figure 2 but showing a selection exhibiting varying behaviours across catchments.

Figure 4 – Annual precipitation, flow and predicted flow state for two catchments, as produced by HydroState. For the middle row of panels, the hollow circles mark expected flow if the catchment had exhibited no shift—that is, the difference between the hollow and filled circles gives the “missing” flow for a given year.

Figure 5 – Proportion of catchments shifted over time with the number of samples in a given year annotated. “Normal” means the same flow state as in 1975, or the earliest recorded year thereafter (this year varies by catchment). “High” means a flow state that gives more annual streamflow for a given rainfall, than the “normal” state; “low” means the opposite. “Very low” means that the streamflow was so anomalously low that an extra state below “low” gave the best outcome (judged by AIC).

Figure 6 – Locations of catchments shifted, for different points in time. Catchments missing streamflow data for the year indicated are shown with a grey outline.

Figure 7 – The estimated magnitude of shifts in the rainfall-runoff relationship for each catchment (quantified by the amount of missing, or surplus water).

2.3.3 Relationship between hydrological non-stationarity and land cover

Figure 8 shows the split of land cover for each catchment, where the catchments are themselves grouped by whether non-stationarity is exhibited, with a distinction made between those that shifted to low or very low flow states, those which did not shift, and those which exhibited flow in high flow states (noting not all of the catchments are reported – see Section 2.2). Catchments exhibiting hydrological non-stationarity towards less streamflow are mostly covered in trees; whereas the others tend to have a higher proportion associated with land cover other than trees. Interestingly, some of the cleared catchments that transitioned from normal to low flow did so later than other more forested catchments (i.e. Catchments 617003 and 604001 shifting in 2005, and Catchment 616001 shifting in 2010 (See Appendix A.2)). For such catchments, it may have taken longer for the drier climate to take effect, possibly because they were mid-way through equilibrating to land clearing, as discussed further in Section 2.4. A small number of heavily forested catchments displayed non-stationarity towards higher flow, counter to expectations. However, these catchments switched back by the year 2000 to normal flow state, and subsequently they either remained in the normal state (Catchment 603005) or switched to the dry state in 2010 (Catchments 614044 and 616216).

Finally, Figure 9 shows the relationship between the magnitude of the non-stationarity and the proportion of the catchment covered by the land cover category “closed forest”. While there is considerable scatter about the line of best fit, there is a correlation with the non-stationarity shift magnitude—recall from Section 2.2 that this is quantified as the average annual difference between the solid and hollow circles in Figure 4 above. This correlation may indicate that forest cover causes a catchment to be more likely to exhibit non-stationarity. A possible hypothesis is that deep rooted vegetation is well-placed to extract what water it needs, with streams only receiving the excess water (if any), leading to a non-linear response. Alternatively, it may be that other factors (themselves correlated

with forest cover) are driving this behaviour, such as if forest cover were correlated with regional groundwater flow systems that tend to export water away from local streams. A further possible explanation is that groundwater recharge is more sensitive to climate in non-stationarity areas, causing groundwater levels to decline rapidly under small declines in rainfall, and become disconnected with surface runoff. Many of these factors are considered further in the literature review below.

Figure 8: Catchment land cover proportions stratified by whether non-stationarity is absent or present, with the latter case subdivided according to whether a high or low flow state is observed. The category “land cover associated with trees other than closed forest” is the sum of three categories, namely: “open forest”, “open woodland” and “sparse woodland” (land cover from <https://researchdata.edu.au/dynamic-land-cover-version-21/1278349>).

Figure 9: Relationship between the proportion of a catchment occupied by closed forest and the magnitude of the shift in rainfall-runoff relationship (quantified by the amount of missing, or in a few cases, surplus, water).

2.4 Literature review of dominant processes and drivers

We begin this literature review with a region-by-region approach, considering the varied landscapes of the south west. We then review the interactions among drivers associated with climate and land use, and how this is mediated by groundwater as an expression of the “memory” of the catchment. Lastly, we return to the results just presented and discuss these in light of the literature review, including implications for rainfall-runoff modelling.

2.4.1 Review by region

Streamflow can be classified based on how it traverses the landscape, being either throughflow/interflow, overland flow or baseflow, with specific geological and topographical properties triggering each flow behaviour (George and Conacher, 1993), while also being driven by climatological patterns. The study area in south west Western Australia covers a wide span of these categories, creating complexity when predicting water availability within the region, even prior to introducing the further challenge of a changing climate. While the soil properties show variation at the local scale from catchment divides to the valley floors (Sharafi et al. 2005), the major landforms which these soils have been weathered from can help to partition common processes which dictate flow. The Darling Plateau is formed over and weathered from the Yilgarn Craton, which is separated to the West from the Perth Basin by the Darling Fault, movement of which resulted in the Darling Ranges (Bell, 2007). To the South, the Jarrahwood Axis and Stirling Range form a less severe boundary with the Albany-Fraser Orogen.

Coastal Plains (Swan and Scott in Perth Basin, Albany Area)

The Coastal Plains within the Perth Basin (Scott and Swan) and along the Albany-Fraser Orogen are characterised by highly permeable soil profiles, with either limestone or deep sands immediately bordering the ocean and sandy dunal systems progressing inland (Bell, 2007; Stuart-Street et al., 2007). These areas are generally low lying, with elevations below 150m AHD (Ali et al., 2012a), only a minor volume of groundwater moves laterally (Gelsinari et al., 2024). The soils range in depth but are permeable and have poor water holding capacity (Gelsinari et al., 2024), and as such, are easily filled by winter rains; shallow perched storage is also commonplace (McFarlane et al., 2020; Bell, 2007). Streams rarely develop in these regions, but those formed are dominated by saturation excess runoff, which may occur in a highly non-linear fashion in these flat landscapes. Alternatively, groundwater flow may be important where the superficial aquifers intercept with the water table. Either way, the streamflow generation mechanisms are highly dependent on groundwater in these coastal plains.

Urbanisation along the coastline has reduced the volume of precipitation intercepted and transpired by vegetation (McFarlane et al., 2020), thus, despite a historic decline in rainfall, groundwater level projections have suggested little to no change across most of the Perth Basin, with the exception of the Gnangara mound (Dawes et al., 2012; Ali et al., 2012a; McFarlane et al., 2020). Recent review of studies concerning recharge within the Gnangara groundwater system has confirmed this projection, most prominently in locations where native vegetation cover is still dominant, noting that the depth to water table is increasing disproportionately with declining rainfall (Gelsinari et al., 2024). Extrapolating recharge patterns from caves within this area has reiterated this phenomenon and confirmed that current patterns are an unprecedented decline in groundwater recharge (Priestly et al., 2023), possibly associated with reduced intensity of winter storms and the preferential recharge it triggers (Priestly et al., 2023).

Increasing stress has been put on groundwater sources within coastal regions due to population expansion and greater demand – for example, the groundwater under Albany was allocated at 120% of its sustainable limit as of 2012 (Dawes et al., 2012). Depending on soil properties, drawdown from these practices may be dissipated over wide areas (Dogramaci, 2004), meaning groundwater decline may appear more muted. Furthermore, poor well placement and high abstraction has resulted in seawater intrusion threatening the consumptive value of fresh groundwater stores (Costall et al. 2020; Ali et al. 2012a; McFarlane et al. 2012). This is exacerbated in some locations by sea level rise and land subsidence triggered by groundwater extraction (Featherstone et al. 2012). Some early implementation of wastewater recharge is being conducted within the Perth Basin to contend with rising demand (Bekele et al. 2015; Bekele et al., 2019), however, the volume of recharge is not currently sufficient to mitigate previous demand impacts. Overall, given the dependence on groundwater of the dominant streamflow mechanisms in these coastal plains, these aspects of vulnerability of groundwater resources extend also to streamflow within coastal basins.

Blackwood and Dandaragan Plateaux

The Blackwood Plateau is inland and elevated from the coastal plain, bounded to the east by the Darling Fault, with soils featuring a higher clay content and lowered hydraulic conductivity (Bell, 2007; McFarlane et al., 2020). The groundwater within these regions is connected to that underlying the Perth Basin (Hu et al. 2019), but has been flagged as more vulnerable than the coastal plains in future projections (Ali et al., 2012a). The region is still largely forested (McFarlane et al., 2020), meaning the majority of rainfall is intercepted and little remains for recharge, and similarly trees may be an important control on water availability for streamflow. Combined with its elevation, the lower recharge results in generally higher depths to the water table (Hu et al., 2019). As such, regional reductions from abstraction have exacerbated the vulnerability of groundwater storage (Ali et al., 2012a). This contrasts with the Dandaragan Plateau, a landform north of Perth, also elevated and separated from the coast and Darling Ranges. Gravelly and sandy soils within this region, paired with extensive clearing for dryland agriculture mean that despite it being in a lower rainfall zone, a greater volume of precipitation is available for recharge (McFarlane et al., 2020) and thus streamflow.

Darling Ranges, Darling Plateau and Zone of Rejuvenated Drainage

Moving inland north and east, the Darling Ranges and Plateau cover the remainder of the study area. Typically, soils are duplex (Sharafi et al., 2005), the upper horizon of which is easily saturated by winter rains which triggers saturation excess overland or shallow throughflow. Ponding within the Darling Plateau has been noted to not always follow topography, with extruding clay formations suggested as the driving contributor (Tennant et al., 1992). Groundwater movement has also been found along the Darling Fault, with research suggesting this formation facilitates preferential flow and movement across catchment boundaries (Clarke et al., 1998).

Local climatic conditions range from high rainfall along the Darling Fault to low rainfall progressing east (Hayes and Garnaut, 1981). Higher rainfall zones have a well leached soil profile and produce fresh water supplies, which were a major source of potable water for Perth (Dawes et al., 2012) prior to the declining dam inflows linked to reduced rainfall (Bates et al., 2010). Declining rainfall has reduced the proportion of annual rainfall available for recharge where high coverage of natural vegetation remains, increasing the depth to groundwater in some locations (Dawes et al., 2012; Kinal and Stoneman, 2012).

Salt stores within the soil increase moving inland towards the medium and low rainfall zones (Stokes et al., 1980), often associated with spatial patterns in land use. Depth to groundwater, while influenced by topography generally (Shafari et al., 2005), follows a similar but opposing trend to salinity, generally increasing for lowered annual precipitation (Kinal and Stoneman, 2012). Agricultural development of further inland lower rainfall regions necessitated native forest clearing, triggering rising water tables which leached long stored salt into the groundwater and subsequent salinisation of streamflow (Schofield and Ruprecht, 1989) and agricultural land, with the latter the subject of significant remediation efforts (see next paragraph). Depth to water table within cleared catchments is now correlated with the time since clearing (McFarlane et al., 2020; Ruprecht et al., 1991), where previously most rainfall within the region evaporated or was transpired (Hatton et al., 2003).

Due to the homogenous topography along the plateau, groundwater movement is generally slow (Sharafi et al., 2005) and lower lying areas experience ponding and water logging. As such, methods to mitigate dryland salinity and rising water tables, such as drainage lines and targeted revegetation cause local drawdown and only influence streamflow patterns within close proximity (Hatton et al., 2003; Speed and Mahtab, 2001; Pridham, 2010). These remedies are not significant enough to contend with the intensified recharge driven by land clearing. Where revegetation has included tree planting, some studies have shown groundwater flow redirection towards the sink caused (Hatton et al., 2003). While a small seasonal reduction in water table, as prompted by Saltbush planting, showed successful desalinisation of the land (Bennett et al., 2014), attributing its success to mitigating evaporation from water near the soil surface. This suggests the water table may tolerate mild drawdown from shallower rooted vegetation.

2.4.2 Process interactions among climate, land use and groundwater

While the aforementioned characteristics describe a complex landscape within the south west, the magnitude of impact on the rainfall-runoff ratio due to each system input is varied. Land use and its relationship with the changing climate are noted as major contributing factors to the larger system responses observed over the study area, with well-documented relationship to streamflow pattern changes (e.g. Borg et al., 1988a; Borg et al., 1988b), and suggested links to non-stationarity (Kinal and Stoneman, 2012; Hughes et al., 2012).

For cleared lands, the removal of naturally forested lands for agricultural development changed the water balance, as mentioned above. In paired catchment studies, cleared areas showed an immediate sharp rise in streamflow and a following steady incline (Ruprecht and Schofield, 1989). This was suggested to be due to the immediate cessation of interception and transpiration, followed by the continued expansion of the variable source area (repelling further recharge) until an equilibrium was reached. As such, land clearing resulted in an increase in saturation excess runoff, in addition to the direct groundwater discharge contributing to baseflow. Clearing resulted in a dramatic landscape change, with some current streams only developing after clearing (Hatton et al., 2003). Further studies have indicated a reduced hydraulic conductivity of cleared soils (Sharma et al., 1987) which has the potential to slow recharge. However, as evapotranspiration rates of agricultural land have been found lower than forests (McFarlane et al., 1993), changes to soil properties will not sufficiently mitigate water table rise. The groundwater triggered baseflow within cleared regions to the east of the Darling Scarp has a high salinity content (Kinal and Stoneman, 2012; George and Conacher, 1993), meaning little reprieve from the strain on water resources due to a drying climate is provided by the consistent streamflow within these regions. In this area, Callow and Smettem (2006) found that land clearing caused dieback of native vegetation due to the rising saline water table; intensified flows caused further degradation, with remaining native vegetation reserved to higher ground. This indicates that in certain cases, a positive feedback loop may be triggered by clearing land. Groundwater level monitoring over 2007-2012 within cleared areas has shown either stability or a reduction in the rate of rise (Raper et al., 2014), suggesting that equilibrium is being approached, which may be facilitated by reduced recharge associated with reductions in rainfall over recent decades (McFarlane et al., 2020).

In contrast, catchments with remnant native vegetation or plantations have seen a disproportionate response to the drying climate, with the suggestion that a new hydrologic regime has been initiated (e.g. Petrone et al. 2010). A variety of paired catchment studies (Ruprecht and Schofield, 1991; Bari et al., 1996) and studies involving treatment on single catchments (Ruprecht et al., 1993; Silberstein et al., 2013) have been conducted to determine streamflow response to forest disturbance with an increase in streamflow being linked to forest management actions including harvesting, thinning, ringing, clearing and burning. Zhang et al. (2011) noted that paired catchment studies are conducted at scales not representative of areas the size of which water planning decisions are made, however, the time trend analysis they conducted reiterated the integral role of forestry in the water balance. Kinal and Stoneman (2012) monitored groundwater levels and stream salinity in a forested catchment to demonstrate the integral link between groundwater and reduction in rainfall-runoff relationship. Previously, the contribution of groundwater within the region has not been fully considered, with throughflow originating from shallow groundwater noted as the integral component for streamflow generation (Stokes and Loh, 1982; Turner et al., 1987). These short-term studies on small experimental catchments included a hydrograph separation model and an analysis of stable isotope concentrations, both concluding that the majority of the flow generated was from throughflow near the soil surface. Recently these definitions have been contended, with the importance of groundwater contribution being revisited (Grigg and Kinal, 2020; Hughes and Vaze, 2015; Kinal and Stoneman, 2012). Grigg and Kinal (2020), over a long term study and multiple experimental catchments, found that the direct contribution of groundwater to streamflow ranges from 0-90%, indicating greater variability across the region. Groundwater may contribute further in creating saturated areas that enhance both saturation excess overland and throughflow (Raiter, 2012), making it an essential component of streamflow generation.

Despite high evapotranspiration demand and a drying climate, forest cover has remained consistent in some cases, as indicated by satellite imagery (Smettem et al. 2013; Harper et al., 2019), while in other cases exceptionally dry years (such as 2010-11 and 2023-24) have driven die-back. Silberstein et al. (2001) showed that transpiration in Jarrah forests was higher where water tables were shallow, and almost consistent in contrasting seasons. This

indicates the contribution of forests to the depletion of groundwater stores and suggests a role for groundwater in providing a consistent water supply for vegetation. Silberstein et al. (2013) reported that regeneration of forests after treatment lead to an increase in evapotranspiration compared to pre-treatment conditions. Further studies have suggested that sapwood area and vegetation cover of regrowth forests to be significantly higher (Macfarlane et al., 2010; Borg and Stoneman, 1991), indicating these factors may be significant in determining groundwater demand. The extent to which ground water can be accessed, however, is limited. Macfarlane et al. (2018) showed transpiration per unit leaf area within the northern Jarrah forest to be lower where depth to groundwater exceeds 15m. This suggests declining groundwater tables may influence forest mortality, where precipitation is not sufficient to support growth. Harper et al. (2009) reported the role of soil depth and water storage capacity as significant drivers in forest mortality. As rainfall declines and the groundwater level declines, the volume of winter rainfall stored in soil which is accessible to forests may decrease. Accelerated forest mortality has also been found in some patches after periods of more severe drought and increased temperature (Evans and Lyons, 2013). Thinning of forests due to mortality (gradual or widespread), may not trigger a large enough rise in the water table to reinvigorate streamflow, however, with varying intensities of timber harvest in a paired catchment study showing no reversal of the continued decline in groundwater within a Jarrah forest (Kinal and Stoneman, 2011).

In this way, groundwater storage can be considered as storing memory of the water balance from preceding years, whereby if rainfall is lower than is demanded by transpiration, evaporation and other system losses, an overall decline will be seen for that year. This is reiterated by Petrone et al. (2010), who noted that more significant reductions in streamflow in a forested catchment occurred following anomalously low rainfall years, and Hughes et al. (2012) who suggested that the decline in groundwater may only be remediated with correspondingly positive anomalous rainfall. Given the general agreement of global circulation models for a drier climate in SWWA, high rainfall years are less likely in the future than they have been in the past (Dawes et al. 2012).

2.4.3 Synthesis and discussion

In summary, many areas have been the subject of significant groundwater declines, in contrast to non-forested areas whose historical clearing has often led to decadal (and in some cases ongoing) increases in groundwater levels. The literature review emphasises the importance of the distinct hydrogeology of many areas within the south-west, and its interaction with land use changes. Overall, the long hydrological "memory" of groundwater systems is an important driver of interannual and decadal river flow dynamics.

We now briefly consider the links with the results shown above. Despite a significant rainfall breakpoint in the 1970s (Hope et al., 2006; Priestly et al., 2023) and visual changes to the rainfall-runoff relationship seen in the linear regression plots, most flow state changes did not occur until after 2000 according to the Hidden Markov modelling. The decline in rainfall has shown correlation with declining groundwater levels across the same period (Kinal and Stoneman, 2012), and a rainfall decline has been noted to have occurred in steps, with the second in 2000 (Priestley et al., 2023). This reiterates the review above, suggesting a disconnection of groundwater from surface water may be a key driver in some catchments. Further, data availability may be impacting results, with data from only 39 catchments available in 1975.

The shifted catchments indicated a significant and strong negative relationship with high density forests, suggesting that, with rainfall decline, forests may cause a large decrease to the proportion of rainfall that becomes runoff. In contrast, clearing for agricultural development has shown historic decreases in infiltration and increases recharge and runoff (Hatton et al. 2003). While "stable" catchments (i.e. those not exhibiting non-stationarity) tended to have less tree cover, the interpretation of this is unclear: the obvious answer is to take this at face value (cleared catchments are more resilient), but many of these catchments may have been mid-way through trends in groundwater levels due to clearing, to which the drier climate since the 1970s provided a partial antidote. If so, it is possible that many seemingly "stable" catchments would indeed have been vulnerable to recent dry conditions, had they already finished their re-equilibration and a new steady-state had been attained earlier.

While links between non-stationarity and groundwater have been proven in some studies, and the data indicates this may be consistent across a wider area, confirmation for a given site should be achieved through consultation with groundwater data, a step which was not possible in this study due to difficulties with the timing of data provision. In

any case, it seems reasonable (based on the above review) to assume that groundwater plays a key role in modulating rainfall-runoff response in most, if not all, catchments considered in this study. For modelling, this is a significant finding, since it is known that many simple rainfall-runoff models lack the capacity to store and replicate trends in groundwater which span multi-annual to multi-decadal periods (Fowler et al., 2020). Attempts to update models to include this process have shown some improvement compared to baseline models (e.g. Grigg and Hughes, 2018; Hughes et al., 2021), and accordingly the next section has a special focus on models that explicitly attempt to replicate the long, slow dynamics of groundwater systems.

3 Improved modelling of hydrological non-stationarity

Rainfall-runoff models are a useful tool for predicting water availability, however, their predictive capacity can be limited where processes within a region are not adequately represented in the model structure. Some models show particularly good performance in certain regions, while not in others, and there is a wide array of models available for use, making selection of a suitable model complicated. Existing studies testing models in the south west have been limited in both the number of catchments and the models used (e.g. Hughes et al., 2021; Fowler et al., 2016). In response, this project has aimed to test a broader range of models across a wider catchment set than previously.

The predictive capacity of models is further influenced by how the parameters are fit to the data via calibration. Standard practice is to calibrate models through the optimisation of an objective function, which determines how the “match” with observations is mathematically defined. Many objective functions have been created, and they may differ in the weight they afford to high versus low flow conditions, dry versus wet years, or bias in the total flow volumes. These considerations become particularly important in the context of a drying climate, and the testing of several objective functions (as described below) is intended to explore this further.

3.1 Questions explored via modelling tests

This section aims to answer three questions, as outlined in Figure 10. The first two questions are both about the ability of models to perform adequately when presented with multi-year periods of contrasting climatic conditions. These two questions may seem similar but are separated by important distinctions. In the first case, we ask whether a given model can match the overall trends in streamflow over recent decades. This question is asked without any restriction on the amount or type of data that is “shown” to the model via calibration. In contrast, the second question is about extrapolation, or the ability of the model to operate in conditions unlike those it was calibrated to. This implies that we must restrict the data “shown” to the model such that we reserve some (in this case, a dry period in the historic record) so that the model can be tested in conditions unlike those it saw during calibration. This is analogous to climate change impact studies whereby the future climatic conditions may be unlike those of the past, yet the model is still expected to operate reliably. In contrast, the first question is more about the inherent capabilities of the model, regardless of the specific manner in which it is calibrated or what data is withheld. Lastly, a third question explores what difference it makes adopting the techniques that arise as the most favourable from the previous two tests. This is explored using a basic future climate scenario. We now explain the method for these modelling exercises, and each test in turn is described in Sections 3.2.1 to 3.2.3.

Figure 10 – Questions to be answered by this report and the adopted test implemented.

3.2 Methods for each test

3.2.1 Coverage test

This test has its origins in efforts to separate the inherent capabilities of models from the specific choices made in calibration (Fowler et al., 2018). Since we seek models that can perform adequately over contrasting climatic conditions, the test first involves defining different multi-year periods with contrasting conditions and defining two or more axes representing model performance over these different periods (Figure 11). This results in a performance “space”. The purest form of the coverage test involves generating and individually testing a very large sample of parameter sets chosen via random selection; i.e. without calibration. Although most such parameter sets will perform terribly, some will fall closer to what might be considered “good” performance. If we repeat the random sampling continuously and plot each parameter set into the performance space, a cloud of outcomes will begin to appear, and eventually the upper boundary of the cloud will become evident, with the capabilities of the model expressed as the degree of “coverage” of the performance space.

This form of the test is computationally inefficient due to the need to run a very large random sample of parameter sets before the cloud edge becomes clear. A more efficient alternative is to use a multi-objective optimiser to define only the upper boundary of interest (Figure 11), which is what is done here, using the AMALGAM optimiser (Vrugt et al., 2007). Regardless of the adopted method to define the boundary, the ability of the model to perform robustly under changing climate can be characterised by identifying the point on the upper boundary that is closest to the point in the space that corresponds to perfect model performance. Inter-model comparison can proceed by either a comparison of these distances (closer means a better model) or via direct comparison of the curves themselves. Note that the objective functions used are outlined in Section 3.3.

Figure 11 – Coverage upper boundary of two hypothetical models, with the minimum distance marked from their coverage to the location of perfect performance. In this report, the “dry period” is defined as the 7 driest consecutive years (by streamflow), while the “nondry period” is defined as the rest of the historic record (for the streamflow gauge in question).

3.2.2 Differential split sample test

This test has some similarities with the coverage test described in the previous region—both involve the separation of the historic record into sub-periods based on climatic conditions. However, in the Differential Split Sample Test (Klemes et al., 1986), the model is calibrated directly to one of the periods and not the other. The other is then used for independent evaluation (i.e. validation) of the model, specifically testing its ability to simulate reliably in conditions different from the calibration data. In this research, we use CMA-ES (Hansen et al., 2004), a well known single-objective optimiser, as the optimisation algorithm, following dozens of hydrological studies in the academic literature. To characterise the impact of objective function selection, several different objective functions are tested, as outlined in Section 3.3.

3.2.3 Climate change test

To determine whether the methods explored made much difference to streamflow projections under a future climate, the parameters found through calibration were run with a simple climate change scenario. This scenario was based on scaled historic climatic data as input, with scaling factors based on the National Hydrological Projections Assessment for an RCP8.5 emissions scenario in 2050 (Wilson et al., 2022). In line with this source, historic data were scaled with a 10% increase in PET, 20% reduction in precipitation from May to October and 5% reduction in precipitation for the remainder of the year (Turner et al., 2022). Outcomes were assessed with reference to the runoff-ratios for different model simulations.

3.3 Methodological and data considerations applicable to all tests

3.3.1 Data

The same catchment set and information sources were used as the previous analysis – see Section 2.2.1 for details.

3.3.2 Model selection

Models were selected in collaboration with DWER and presented to a wider group of experts prior to finalisation. These were considered an extensive list which covered a broad range of model structures, each with varying strengths. The models selected and their reasoning for inclusion are noted in Table 3. All testing of models was conducted through the open source MARRMoT framework (Trotter et al., 2022) in MATLAB, which contains 46 hydrological models and allows for consistent inter-model comparison.

3.3.3 Objective function selection

Objective functions were selected in a similar way to the models. As mentioned, several objective functions were tested to determine which are best for use under changing climatic conditions. Objective functions are presented in Table 4 with their relevance and their equations. One important point was the selection of one objective function to serve as the benchmark objective function, used (i) in the coverage test to define model performance across the different periods; and (ii) in the split sample tests to provide a point of comparison for objective function testing (the undesirable alternative being to only evaluate split sample results against the adopted objective function in each case, thus precluding the possibility of intercomparison). On discussion with DWER, the Split Trotter was adopted as the benchmark objective function. This was because of its shared emphasis on low and high flows, reducing model bias, and paying equal attention to all years, ensuring drier years are not neglected in the model analysis.

Table 3 – Models selected for evaluation

Model	Characteristics and reasoning for inclusion
GR4J (Perrin et al., 2003)	A simple 4-parameter conceptual bucket model with a history of use in SWWA.

SACRAMENTO (Burnash, 1995)	Model with much greater complexity (11 parameters and 5 storages) is currently being used in work regarding the Murray Darling Basin.
SIMHYD (Chiew et al., 2002)	Another legacy model, with greater complexity. Is commonly used throughout Australia, with generally good performance, some exceptions where catchments are dry or ephemeral.
IHACRES (Croke and Jakeman, 2004)	A low complexity model which includes accounting for moisture deficit within a catchment, with aims to better incorporate the influence of land use and climate. Has shown good performance under changing climates.
GR4J-DD (Fowler et al., 2021)	An alteration of GR4J which allows for the tracking of deficit within soil moisture due to climate drying and as such it better predicts streamflow after periods of drought. Testing of this model had not yet been conducted in the study region.
GR4J-SGW-inter (Fowler, in prep.)	Recent further alterations of GR4J developed with the express intention of better replication of multiyear groundwater dynamics. These have successfully been tested in eastern Australia but had no history of use in SWWA.
GR4J-SGW-intra (Fowler, in prep.)	
LASCAM (Sivapalan et al., 1996)	A complex model developed specifically for use in Western Australia, with good performance shown in the past. For incorporation into the modelling framework, the LAI parameter was set to 1. Note, code for LASCAM was based directly on DWER-provided code.
GR7J (Grigg and Hughes, 2018)	An alteration of GR4J which aimed to better represent the catchment “memory” stored in groundwater and incorporate changes in vegetation cover over time. For incorporation into the modelling framework, the LAI parameter was set to 1 (removing a parameter from GR8J). This model was used to assess the Southern Forest Irrigation Scheme (Hughes and Wang, 2022).

Table 4 – Objective functions selected for testing in the Differential Split Sample Test

Objective Function	Formula	Properties
Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE; Nash & Sutcliffe, 1970)	$1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{NumDays} (Q_{sim} - Q_{obs})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{NumDays} (Q_{obs} - \mu(Q_{obs}))^2}$	An improvement on the mean squared error and is most used in industry.
Kling Gupta Efficiency (KGE; Gupta et al., 2009)	$1 - \sqrt{(r - 1)^2 + (\alpha - 1)^2 + (\beta - 1)^2}$ where, r is the Pearson correlation coefficient, $\alpha = \frac{\sigma(Q_{sim})}{\sigma(Q_{obs})}$ $\beta = \frac{\mu(Q_{sim})}{\mu(Q_{obs})}$	Overcomes problems with the NSE in which high bias and NSE could coexist within a sufficiently variable timeseries. This is the most used in academia.
Trotter (Trotter et al., 2023)	$\frac{1}{2} (KGE_Q + KGE_{Q^{0.2}}) - 5 \cdot \log_e(B + 1) ^{2.5}$ where, $B = \frac{\mu(Q_{sim})}{\mu(Q_{obs})} - 1$	Aims at solving the tendency of the NSE and KGE to preference matching of high flows through the inclusion of a low flow component. Includes the bias penalty term commonly used in modelling by CSIRO.
Split Trotter	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{NumYears} Trotter_i}{\sum NumYears}$	Aims to rectify the tendency to ignore dry years in the calibration process (Fowler et al., 2018) through calculating the objective function for each year and averaging across years.
Split Trotter Weighted	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{NumYears} Trotter_i \times \omega_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{NumYears} \omega_i}$ where, $\omega_i = \left(\frac{1}{\log_e(Q_i)}\right)^{1.5}$	Aims to place additional emphasis on model fitting to drier years by assigning a weight to every year. Weighting function determined in collaboration with DWER.

3.4 Results

3.4.1 Coverage Testing

Figure 12 presents coverage tests for all models and for a selection of catchments in the Warren-Donnelly region. The shape of the coverage boundaries indicate there is not undue trade-off between performance in the different periods, which is promising. To a reader familiar with NSE values, the values shown here may seem low, but it must be remembered that the Split Trotter objective function is a much more difficult challenge for models due to the need to have consistent performance across all years in the period and across high and low flows. In terms of model choice, the results show that these catchments LASCAM appears to be the best choice, with Baker Road Crossing and Lefroy Brook also showing preference to GR4J-SGW-inter and Bulilup preferring SACRAMENTO. See Appendix B.1 for the complete coverage test results.

Figure 12 – Coverage test results for all models and a selection of catchments, focussing on the Warren-Donnelly region.

Due to the difficulty of showing so many coverage boundary curves, the model performance is summarised as described in Section 3.2.1; namely, as the distance from the point of optimal performance on the coverage front to the point of perfect performance. Boxplots of this value across the multiple catchments can be seen in Figure 13. The sample size of this figure is restricted to 74, as the LASCAM model runs did not complete for 2 catchments. Despite this, Figure 13 demonstrates LASCAM as having the best available performance comparative to the alternative models, with the highest median around 0.9, and significantly less spread in the results than other models. The next most suitable models appear to be SACRAMENTO and GR4J-SGW-inter, with minimum distances also around 1 (note for this test that lower values reflect better model performance).

These results are shown spatially in Figure 14. LASCAM showed strongest performance to the south-west, the portion of the Darling Ranges approaching the Blackwood Plateau. GR4J showed poor performance to the south near Albany and to the east of Perth, with only a few select catchments achieving closer to optimal performance. The northernmost and easternmost catchments showed poor performance across all models (see Appendix B.1.3 for comprehensive maps). Although these results are promising, an overall assessment must first consider the other two tests.

3.4.2 Differential split sample testing

The performance of each model when calibrated using each of the 5 objective functions is shown in Figure 15. Recall from Section 3.2.2 that the overall purpose of the differential split sample test is to determine if the model can perform under climatic conditions that are different to those under which it was calibrated. Here we repeat this with several objective functions to determine if the choice of objective function makes a difference to the outcome. The sample has been restricted again to just those of which the LASCAM calibration had completed running, with the number of samples used to construct each boxplot displayed (see Appendix B.2 for full sample of results). The boxplots indicate low performance in split sample testing in general, with the least bad performance seen through either LASCAM or GR4J-SGW-intra, when calibrated using either Split Trotter or Weighted Split Trotter. The variation in model performance is not large, however, the median performance can only be seen in the LASCAM which has been calibrated using the Split Trotter objective function. The majority of medians are thus below -0.5. Further to this, some of the models calibrated using the KGE and NSE have an upper quartile below -0.5, with just the tail of the plot visible. Thus, it is clear that the model performance in extrapolation leaves much to be desired. This result, which is consistent with other studies conducted in Australia and elsewhere, is discussed in Section 3.5.

Figure 13 – Distance from model coverage boundary to the point of perfect performance. Box plots show distribution of values spatially (i.e. one value per catchment). Note that lower values are desirable; 0 means perfect model performance.

Figure 14 – Spatial variation in coverage test performance for selected models.

Figure 15 – Box plots indicating differential split sample performance of each model when calibrated to each objective function. Results refer to model performance during an independent evaluation period that is drier than the calibration period. Results are reported using the benchmark objective function (Split Trotter).

3.4.3 Climate change test

Climate change test results are shown in Figure 16, specifically the runoff ratios for given annual average precipitation for selected combinations of models and objective functions. As mentioned, the test is intended to quantify the difference made when the best models and objective functions are adopted, as identified in the previous tests. For this purpose, we have adopted as the best models LASCAM and GR4J-SGW-Intra; and the Weighted Split Trotter as the best objective function. Results are then compared to a combination intended to represent current practice in Industry – namely GR4J calibrated with NSE. For the selected catchments, GR4J calibrated using the NSE is consistently higher than LASCAM and GR4J-SGW-Intra calibrated using the Weighted Split Trotter. GR4J also consistently predicts a higher runoff ratio than is observed. LASCAM is often closest to the observed runoff ratio for the Historic Driest 7 Years, but not always to the remaining Historic Years. Although the future scenario has no “observed” by definition, LASCAM often has the lowest runoff ratio in the projected drier future. Thus, if model choice were made on the precautionary principle alone, LASCAM would seem to be a good candidate relative to the other options here. This pattern is mainly consistent with the remainder of the results (Appendix B.3.1) with some outliers.

It is recommended that the climate change test be used as an extra check to ensure simulated future streamflow is realistic. The essence of the check is that the simulated streamflow should not contradict the observed relationship between mean annual rainfall and rainfall-runoff ratio. For example, In some cases in Figure 16, the modelled drier future climate has a runoff ratio greater than (GR4J in Sleeman Road Bridge and Ngangaguringuring) or the same as (GR4J in Rocky Glen) the Historic Driest 7 years, despite there being a lowered average annual precipitation. In these

cases, where the observed runoff ratio declines between the dry and non-dry periods, the prediction of an increased runoff ratio in a drier future is unrealistic, and as such this model is likely not suited for modelling these catchments for future scenarios. The modelled future runoff ratio should follow a similar declining trend to the observed (purple points), or at least a monotonic trend (i.e. should not increase if rainfall decreases) for a more robust prediction.

To understand the behaviour of a given catchment relative to those surrounding it, the observed runoff ratio for the dry (Historic Driest 7 Years) and non-dry periods (remainder of the Historic period) for the five nearest catchments with less average annual precipitation were added to the plot. Runoff ratios relating to the same neighbouring catchment are connected by a line. For dry catchments, such as Ngangaguringuring, the catchments with the next least precipitation were plot. In most cases, these show a steep decrease in runoff ratio from the non-dry to dry periods. In Rocky Glen, and to some extent Mount Frankland, the decrease in runoff ratio follows a similar trend to the observed of the catchment of interest. In other neighbouring catchments, however, the decrease is sharper. Interestingly, some neighbouring catchments for Sleeman Road Bridge show a decrease in runoff ratio, but an increase in average annual precipitation, reflecting that precipitation is not the only driver of streamflow dynamics.

Figure 16 – Runoff ratio for a given average annual precipitation across two historic time periods and a hypothetical future climate change run. Note, “historic” is shorthand for “historic period excluding the 7 driest consecutive years”. As noted in the text, adopted simulations should follow a monotonic relationship when compared to observed data – so, for example, the GR4J simulations for the future period would be rejected for 603007 and 616013 because they exceed the observed runoff ratio over the seven driest years despite the fact that these years were wetter than the future period. Note that the greyed data is for context only.

3.4.4 Inspection of timeseries

Figure 17 displays the daily timeseries of three of the above catchments during the driest historic year used during evaluation. Simulated and observed streamflow are on the bottom x-axis, with precipitation shown above. The combinations of model and objective function are adopted from the climate change test. In the three catchment examples, GR4J and GR4J-SGW-intra over-predict peak flow events, while LASCAM shows under-prediction. Both LASCAM and GR4J-SGW-intra show some persistence of streamflow consistent with the Helena River. These findings are broadly consistent with some of the remaining catchments (Appendix B.3.2).

Figure 17 – Time-series of evaluation year with lowest observed streamflow, plot with simulated streamflow and observed precipitation.

3.5 Discussion

While some models have shown significantly greater performance than others, and have demonstrated robustness in many of the catchments, all models lack capacity in extrapolating flow predictions to climatic conditions different to those in the calibration period. The split sample results show that across the board the median performance is below -0.5, suggesting a lack of robustness in performance of models under extrapolation to the drying climate of the south west. This suggests the need for ongoing research to improve these outcomes, as discussed in Section 4 below.

In contrast, the coverage tests showed more separation among models, which can inform recommendations for model choice. The median distance from perfect performance for some models was undesirably high, including for both GR4J and SIMHYD. This indicates that these model structures cannot sufficiently simulate the streamflow patterns in south west rivers, even when no limits are placed on the data provided to the models. As such, it is recommended that these models be avoided in favour of the better performing models such as LASCAM.

Some of the better performing models exhibit certain features that may help to explain their results. For example, LASCAM has a three store system, in contrast with simpler models which exhibit only two. In the latter case the two stores are typically used, respectively, to (i) track catchment wetness (usually called the “soil moisture store”) and (ii) to add appropriate attenuation to streamflow hydrographs (usually called the “baseflow store”). This leaves no storage for tracking the longer term “memory” of the catchment, mediated via groundwater. In contrast, LASCAM has a specific store for this purpose (the “B” store). Further, having been developed in this region, LASCAM has other features which may be relevant, such as the ability to generate runoff both at the surface and within the soil horizon; this may represent perched groundwater that builds up when infiltrated water reaches a less permeable part of the soil profile. Other models that performed relatively well included GR4J-inter and -intra, altered versions of GR4J that have a slow (non-episodic) leakage of groundwater, either internally within the catchment (-intra) or across the catchment boundary (-inter). The better performance for the -inter version may reflect the ability of this conceptualisation to represent groundwater export to regional systems, which can be an important process in the south west region.

Regarding objective functions, traditional options such as the NSE and KGE exacerbated poor model performance in the split sample calibration, with the third quartile of some model evaluations lower than -0.5. The split sample results supported the adoption of the Weighted Split Trotter or the Split Trotter in preference to the more commonly used NSE and KGE.

Overall, LASCAM showed the greatest robustness in the tests conducted, with the smallest median distance from perfect performance in the coverage testing and a marginally improved result in the split sample testing. Also, given LASCAM had a consistently lower runoff ratio in the climate change tests, its adoption is consistent with precautionary principles under uncertainty. This is emphasised where the LASCAM results more closely follow the trend in neighbouring catchments, such as seen in Mount Frankland (Figure 16).

Spatially, the results did vary, however. LASCAM showed very good performance in several catchments, but in others was outperformed by some of the worse performing models, i.e. GR4J in Catchment 606218. Interestingly, this catchment showed high performance across the board, with LASCAM producing one of the worst scores. Contrastingly, LASCAM showed repeatedly the best performance in catchments with the worst fitting models such as 601001 and 616002, albeit still a substantial distance from perfect performance. Both of these catchments exhibit incredibly variable flows, including some years with no flow, while Catchment 606218 had consistently high flows. This indicates that LASCAM has a greater capacity to predict complicated behaviour within a catchment, in particular, under drought conditions and/or ephemeral streamflow.

3.6 Limitations

While LASCAM has been flagged as the better performing model, some troubleshooting was required for it to be implemented. Further to this, the running of LASCAM in both split sample calibration and coverage testing was much extended when compared to the other models, even those with a similar number of parameters and model complexity. The implementation of the model exactly as written in DWER's existing code may have added to the runtime of the model, which meant that some results were unavailable in this report (the University of Melbourne's High Performance Computer has wall time limits on the duration of calibration tasks). Due to the length of time taken to calibrate in AMALGAM, tolerances required slacking, as it frequently reverted to the slowest solving option, and parameter ranges defined by DWER required compressing. This may be attributed to the complexity of the model, how it interacts with the framework it was implemented in, or how it interacts with specific flow relationships – as the length of time was consistently extended with a select few catchments (Catchment IDs 616216, 603003, 612014 and 610005 amongst a few of the catchments struggled with).

Based on these problems, it is recommended (see below in Next Steps) that efforts be made to simplify the LASCAM model. This is discussed further below. The difficulties in the coding framework adopted here (MARRMoT) need not translate to operational difficulties for DWER, as this framework is only intended as a venue for model intercomparison. In the long term, all outcomes need to be coded into frameworks currently used by DWER, such as Source. However, it is our understanding that LASCAM is also problematic in Source, particularly with respect to long calibration times. This can be problematic in particularly large and complex applications. Thus, regardless of implementation, it would be good to simplify LASCAM where possible.

As described in Section 2.4, forests and their associated evapotranspiration rates and groundwater use have significant impacts on streamflow generation. Both GR7J and LASCAM have parameters pertaining to the LAI of a given catchment which are calibratable. Due to the need for fair intercomparison between models, this functionality was switched off for these tests. Further research may include revisitation of this functionality and how it may impact model performance. In addition, inclusion of such parameters in models which showed promise such as SACRAMENTO or GR4J-SGW-intra may be worth consideration.

Further to the above, long term groundwater processes are a key driving factor of streamflow generation in SWWA and it appears imperative that models consider this to ensure robustness in their predictive capacity. GR4J-SGW-intra includes a component which aims at emanating multiyear groundwater trends, suggesting a reason for its performance over other models. Additional research into including a similar functionality in LASCAM may be useful in ensuring robustness under a drying climate.

As mentioned previously, catchment selection aimed to avoid those with major diversions or extractions, but this was unavoidable in some cases. To determine the significance of farm dam use on a given catchment, DWER provided modelled streamflow data for the hypothetical case where farm dams were removed from the system. This data was limited in the time covered, and was only available for three locations. Figure 18 displays the yearly aggregated and Box-Cox transformed streamflow data for both the observed streamflow and streamflow modelled without farm dams, connected by a line for a given year. Farm dams impart a discernible impact on streamflow volume, as shown by the vertical offset between modelled and observed flows. However, this vertical offset is still not as large as the shifts arising from comparisons across different periods. This suggests that while the reduction in flow triggered by this use is not inconsequential, it does not directly trigger hydrological non-stationarity. Further consideration of the impact of farm dams, however, may be beneficial in ensuring the robustness of the conclusions drawn. This may include further modelling of flow without farm dams, both increasing the length of period modelled and the number of catchments.

Figure 18 – Annual precipitation and Box-Cox transformed streamflow for catchments which involve use from farm dams. Box-Cox transformed streamflow is presented for the cases where farm dam impact estimates are, and are not, accounted for.

The majority of the catchments selected within this study are Hydrological Reference Stations of the Bureau of Meteorology (Turner, 2012), which limits selection to gauging stations which have experienced less than 10% change in land use upstream. While a recent update resulted in an increased number of stations which fit guidelines, this specific criterion did not change. However, information from DWER (Lauren Miles, 2024) has indicated that the extent of land use change over the historic record within selected catchments has varied to a much larger extent than the limit. Figure 19 highlights a selection of catchments for which land clearing data was available over part of their hydrological record and shows land use change indicated by the data supplied (calculated as the difference between the minimum and maximum cleared area for the catchment in question). A few catchments exhibit a much greater shift in land use change than the threshold. In the Kent, Denmark, Upper Collie and Warren catchments, this is linked to clearing controls instated in 1978, followed by subsequent plantations or revegetation efforts. In the Helena River Catchment, this is attributed to plantation establishment between 1967 and 1980. Thus it is noted that, while extensive drying of the climate has been suggested as a significant driver of non-stationarity, the hydrological response may have in some instances been linked to changes in land use. This is a limitation when working with long-term datasets in the study area, as very few catchments have been exempted from land clearing or other forestry activities.

Figure 19 – A selection of catchments which experienced variation in their proportion of cleared area over the observation record, with the maximum difference in percentage of cleared area shown. (Based on information provided by Lauren Miles (DWER), 2024).

3.7 Recommendations for modelling

Based on the above results, our recommendations for modelling are as follows. These recommendations relate to the case where runoff is required to be simulated for a future climate which has a drier rainfall series than the historical period:

1. That DWER continue to use the LASCAM model for rainfall-runoff simulations.
2. That LASCAM be calibrated using the Weighted Split Trotter objective function.
3. That simulated streamflow under future climate scenarios be sanity checked with reference to the relationship between runoff-ratio and mean annual rainfall – specifically, that this relationship should be monotonic, as discussed above in Section 3.4.3.
4. That the above be treated as interim recommendations as research progresses to resolve issues highlighted by this report, particularly around incorporating process understanding in models and improving the ability of models to extrapolate to unseen conditions.

4 Next steps

To make LASCAM more useable in practice, it is recommended that the model structure is reviewed to understand which parameters contribute the least to the overall flow prediction. Armed with this understanding, it may be possible to produce a simpler version of LASCAM that is both more understandable and quicker/easier to reliably calibrate.

A detailed analysis of groundwater data may help to contextualise various results seen here. Firstly, it may help to explain the spatial patterns of non-stationarity reported in Section 2. It is recommended that DWER's groundwater database be interrogated for groundwater bores within or near those catchments exhibiting non-stationarity, in order to determine if groundwater declines are typically associated with this streamflow behaviour. Such analyses should consider the interacting effects of climate and residual impacts of historic land use changes, particularly land clearing.

It is further recommended that ongoing model review also incorporate a specific analysis of groundwater dynamics with reference to available bore and/or satellite data, to make simulations more robust in catchments experiencing non-stationarity due to groundwater decline. The model results have affirmed the value of altering models to account for slow dynamics arising from groundwater (e.g. GR4J-SGW-inter), and such models could complement LASCAM in ongoing tests.

Research is recommended into revised calibration techniques, including (i) continued focus on objective functions that focus on the most relevant parts of the historical streamflow record; and (ii) methods that use non-streamflow types of information such as actual evapotranspiration and groundwater data. The poor extrapolation results for otherwise robust models (such as LASCAM) may be remedied by giving the model more varied information during calibration, and identifying and emphasising the most relevant aspects of this information.

The methods undertaken here focussed on a large sample of catchments, in order to maximise generalisability. It is recommended that future research complement this large sample approach with detailed studies of selected cases that are deemed to be important to water resource planning and/or representative of broader planning areas.

To ensure more certainty in the role of historical land clearing in long term hydrological responses, further exploration of land use change within the catchments selected should be undertaken. This should include linking the available data on change in percentage cleared area over time with non-stationarity and further investigation of other catchments within the study area to determine if they also experienced significant land use change. This will allow for clearer identification of hydrological non-stationarity triggered by continued drying.

5 Conclusion

Based on the results above, it is recommended that future modelling where runoff is required to be simulated for a future drier climate (i.e. less rainfall than the historical period) is undertaken using LASCAM and an objective function is implemented which equally weights lower flows and preferentially weights lower years, such as the Weighted Split Trotter function. The implementation of these techniques will mitigate the risk of over prediction in a drying climate and provide more confidence in planning.

This project has provided an initial assessment of the regional relevance of current modelling models and procedures to water planning. It is pleasing to see that the results affirm the use of a model that is already actively used by DWER, namely the LASCAM model. At the same time, it has revealed limitations in the transferability of models, with implications for robustness of modelling under climate change. Furthermore, it has revealed spatial patterns in non-stationarity that are, at this stage, only partially explainable, and further analysis is recommended, particularly focussing on groundwater data. More robust understanding and modelling will require ongoing research, and in the meantime this report has provided evidence-based interim recommendations for modelling to support water resource planning.

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7 Appendices

The appendices have been saved as a separate file.